

Geographical Information System Approach to Suitability Assessment of Cassava Production in Southeastern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study applied geographical information system in the study of suitability of cassava production in soils of Southeastern Nigeria. The study was conducted in three states of Southeastern Nigeria namely Anambra, Enugu and Ebonyi. Geology map aided sampling and six parent material was considered which include Ogwashi-Asaba Formation, Imo Clay Shale, Bende-Ameki formation, Ajali Sandstone, Asu River Group, and Afikpo Sandstone. Three profile pits were dug at two selected parent materials from each of the selected states. Hand held GPS receiver was used to geo-referenced all sites. 18 profile pits were dug in total and sampled for laboratory analysis. The rainfall of the study areas ranged from 1200 mm to 3000 mm, temperature ranged from 22⁰C to 37⁰C and relative humidity ranged from 25% to 85% which were optimum for cassava production. Soil texture varied from sandy, clayey and loamy. The soils were generally acidic (pH: 5.47 to 7.14). The total nitrogen (0.3 g/kg to 1.46 g/kg), available phosphorus (6.84 mg/kg to 12.43 mg/kg), exchangeable potassium (0.04 cmol/kg to 0.54 cmol/kg) and cation exchangeable capacity (4.03 cmol/kg to 11.23 cmol/kg) were rated low. For the aggregate suitability for cassava production, the soils studied were currently not suitable (N1) for cassava production due to fertility constraint. The potential suitability score indicated that most of the soils studied were optimum for cassava production when all the fertility constraints were removed. For the descriptive statistics, the log normal transformation was done to the parametric suitability score for cassava (potential) base on Shapiro–Wilk test. The results were skewed to the left with cassava (potential) having the higher outlier (-3.232) and lower coefficient of variation (4.871). The semivariogram results indicated that Exponential model was best fitted for cassava (Current) having none log normal transformation while Spherical Model was best fitted for cassava (Potential) having log normal transformation. Both falls within strong spatial class with cassava (Potential) having the lowest nugget effect (0.011). The result of the cross validation showed that the model made a moderate prediction in the variability of the suitability of the cassava. From the Kriged map for suitability of cassava (Current), all the study areas were not suitable for cassava production with areas in Ebonyi State showing the lowest suitability score. When the fertility constraints were removed (potential) the study area became highly suitable for cassava production with suitability score between 83.99 to 95 covering large area of the study area and very few places indicating moderately suitable.

Key Words: Cassava, Geographical Information System, Suitability, population

Introduction

There is a tremendous increase in global population over the last century. According to United Nation recent research, there are about 7.7 billion people in the world (U.N, 2019). This incredible growth in world population is raising the global demand for food. With the increasing demand of food due to the drastic increase in world population, there is need to outline strategies urgently that will ensure sustainable production of food through a holistic method to soil nutrient management (Jones et al., 2013).

Cassava has been known to serve as buffer against crop failure since it can be grown in marginal soils giving it the potential to eliminate food crises and famine (Anikwe et al., 2018). Cassava is the most popular food crop in Southeastern Nigeria and FAO has ranked it as the seventh largest food staple in the world (Iwuagwu, 2012). Asadu et al. (1999) noted that cassava has the ability to adapt to stress capable of reducing crop production like poor edaphic conditions and irregular rain fall. They also noted that high yield of cassava per unit area of land and labour requirements makes cassava a major component of the farming system in many countries in Africa. The soils of Southeastern Nigeria on which cassava is grown are mostly acidic, low fertility, low organic matter with high level of aluminium. Asadu et al. (1999) reported that in these low fertility soil, cassava gave maximum yields of up to 79–80% after liming while sorghum and maize gave their maximum yields respectively only of 9.5 and 52%. This showed that when good management practices are employed on low fertility and acidic soils of Southeastern Nigeria, cassava performs better than most food crops. Land suitability classification is the appropriateness of a particular type of land for a definite use both for its present condition or the condition after improvements (FAO, 1976). Another strategy for attaining food security and sustain our environment is by detailed studying of the soil by characterization of the soil and land evaluation for various land use types (Esu, 2004). A number of soil characteristics has been reported by many scientists to relate to crop yield and performance (Ande, 2011; Ogunkunle, 2004; Howeler, 2002). Geographic Information System (GIS) is a computer based tool that is considered to be high in performance and it is playing a significant part in water and soil resource management and also in the study of pollution (Coleman et al., 2000). It aids to store, retrieve and analyze various forms of data for the purpose of managing the soil resources and also it presents such information in a way anyone can understand. Systematic handling of data is facilitated to generate information in a format that is easy to understand (Igboekwe et al., 2011). Odekunle et al. (2007) applied GIS in agriculture in Nigeria. They monitored the impacts of variability of rainfall on crop yields in Guinean Savanna part of the country. The objective of this research is to apply Geographical Information System in suitability assessment of cassava production in Southeastern Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Description of Study Area

The study was conducted in the three state of Southeastern Nigeria namely Anambra (Oba, Ojoto, Oraifite, Neni, Nanka, Umuona), Enugu (Ojor, Asaba, Ogurugu, Enugu Ezike, Ovoko, Uhunowere) and Ebonyi (Abofia, Inyimagu, Igbeagu, Amoso, Oziza, Ugwukwu). Anambra State has a coordinate of 6° 20' 0" N, 7° 0' 0" E and an area of 4,844 km² (1,870 sq mi), Enugu States has a coordinate of 6° 27' 10" N, 7° 30' 40" E and an area of 7,161 km² (2,765sq mi) and Ebonyi State has coordinate 6° 15' 0" N, 8° 5' 0" E and an area of 5,533 km² (2,136 sq mi). Generally, the underlying geology consists of heterogeneous materials but the six parent material considered include Asu River Group, Ogwashi-Asaba Formation, Bende-Ameki formation, Ajali Sandstone, Imo Clay Shale, and Afikpo Sandstone. The Southeastern Nigeria has a tropical climate with

humidity and rainfall increasing toward the inland, and typify by uniformly high temperature and a seasonal distribution of rainfall. Anambra has average temperature of 25.9 °C and average rainfall of 1386 mm in a year, Enugu has average temperature of 26.3 °C., and average rainfall is 1730 mm in a year, while Ebonyi has average temperature of 27.7 and average rainfall of 1918 in a year (Source: climate-data.org 2019).

Field Work

Eighteen profile pits were dug and described; three profile pits were dug at each parent material, two parent materials were selected from each state. The description and sampling of the profile pits were conducted base on FAO guidelines (FAO, 2006). Hand held GPS receiver were used to geo-referenced all sites.

Soil Analysis

The soil samples collected from the field work were first of all air dried and sieved with 2mm sieve. Particle size distribution was done using Hydrometer method with Calgon [sodium hexametaphosphate (NaPO₃)₆] solution as dispersant (Gee and Or 2002). Soil pH was determined in 1:2.5 soil/water suspensions (Hendershot et al., 1993). Micro-kjeldahl digestion method was used to determine Total Nitrogen Percentage (Bremner et al., 1982). Exchangeable bases (Na, K, Ca and Mg) was extracted using 1N NH₄OAc. Exchangeable Mg and Ca were determined by ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) titration method. Potassium (K) and Sodium (Na) was measured using flame photometry. Exchangeable acidity was evaluated titrimetrically. The results obtain were used to calculate the values for Effective Cation Exchange Capacity and base saturation. Available phosphorus was colorimetrically determined using Bray (11) method (Olsen et al., 1982).

Land Evaluation Procedure: Non parametric method (FAO, 1979) was use to evaluate the soils by placing them in suitability classes and matching their land characteristic with agronomic requirement. Parametric method was also used for evaluation of soil and rated for Cassava production (Sys, 1991). Both environmental factors (rainfall and temperature) and soil characteristics (soil depth, texture, topography, drainage, soil pH, available phosphorus, organic carbon, total nitrogen, exchangeable cation, base saturation) were used for evaluation. The index of productivity (IP) (both current and potential) was evaluated using the square root method (Khiddir, 1986) of the Storie method (Storie, 1978) which follows the Liebig's Law of the Minimum which states that the local yield of terrestrial plants should be limited by the nutrient that is present in the environment in the least quantity relative to its demands for plant growth. Mathematically it is expressed as follows:

$$IP = A \times \sqrt{\frac{B}{100} \times \frac{C}{100} \times \frac{D}{100} \times \frac{E}{100}} \quad 1$$

Where

A = the overall least characteristic rating

B, C, D and E = the least characteristic ratings of one of the five land quality group (Udoh et al. 2011).

In potential productivity index, the corrective fertility measures were applied, there were no longer fertility constraints. In this case, other qualities except fertility (f) were used to calculate the index of productivity. Just one member of each group of the five land quality groups were used in the calculation because Ogunkunle (1993) stated that a strong correlation exists among members of the same group.

GIS Data model and Geostatistics: Geology maps of each states of interest were acquired which served as guide. The open street map was used to develop the shape files and the GPS

information was also added to the developed shape file in order to place it in the rightful geospatial position with the use of Arc GIS 10.2 software and each parametric data were also digitally encoded in the GIS database to generate the suitability maps. Descriptive Statistics was also performed to monitor the normality of the spatial distribution of the parametric data and log transformation was done to aid interpolation. The ordinary kriging (OK) interpolation method was used for prediction of the values of the unmeasured sites (un-samples locations) in the Geostatistical Wizard of the Geostatistical analyst extension of Arc GIS 10.2 (Wang, 2018). Semivariogram was used to examine the spatial distribution structure of the parametric data based on the regionalized variable theory and intrinsic hypotheses (Nielsen et al., 2003). The Exponential Model (current suitability) and the spherical model was use for the potential suitability base on the best-fit model with the lowest value of residual sum of squares. The spatial dependence was classified according to method detailed by Cambardella et al., (1994). The performance of Ordinary Kriging interpolation method was evaluated using cross-validation technique.

Results and Discussion

Land and Soil Characteristics:

Soil characteristics was taking into consideration, evaluated and related to land qualities affecting the land (Table 1 to 3) The temperature of the study areas ranges from 1200mm to 3000mm with relative humidity between 25% to 85 %.

The topography is less than 7% and most of the study sites were well drained. The soils varied from sandy, clayey and loamy in texture. All the soils studied were generally acidic (pH: 5.47-7.14) as reported by many scientist (Onweremadu et al., 2007; Ahukaemere et al., 2016). The total nitrogen was below 2% and was also rated low according to Landon (1991) nutrient rating for crop production. The low level of total nitrogen could be due to constant loss of nitrogen against its little gain in the humid tropics. The low available phosphorus observed was in line with the work of Idigbo et al., (2008) that revealed that phosphorus is one of the most limiting nutrient element in the tropics especially in acidic soils of Southeastern Nigeria. The potassium content was also considered to be low as reported also by Ndukwu et al., (2015) in soils of Southeastern Nigeria. This could be attributed to intense weathering of parent materials occurring in Southeastern Nigeria. The cation exchangeable capacity was low as also reported by Onweremadu et al., (2011) and Ahukaemere et al., (2016)

Table 5 to Table 7 showed the suitability class scores for cassava production for soils of the study area. The climatic requirements were optimum (S1 100) for all the investigated locations. Likewise, topography and drainage were optimum in most of the sites studied except in two locations in Enugu (Asaba and Ogorugu) and also two locations in Ebonyi state (Igbeagu and Abofia) that were evaluated to be marginally suitable (S3). Topography, pH and base saturation were optimum, available phosphorus and C.E.C. were moderately suitable while exchangeable potassium were temporally unsuitable in all soils studied. The depth was also mostly optimum in all the sites studied except in Igbeagu and Abofia where it was marginally suitable. In Enugu State, total nitrogen was mostly, moderately suitable except in soils of Uhunowerre where it was marginally suitable. Texture was optimum in Asaba and Enugu-Ezike and moderately suitable in other sites. Organic matter was optimum in all in soils except in Uhunowerre where it was moderately suitable.

Table 1. Land/Soil Characteristics of the Sites in Enugu States

Land characteristics	Ojor Pedon 1	Asaba Pedon 2	Ogwurugwu Pedon 3	Uhunowere Pedon 4	Ovoko Pedon 5	Enugu- Ezike Pedon 6
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	1200-2000	1200-2000	1200-2000	1200-2000	1200- 2000	1200-2000
Temperature (°C)	22-36	22-36	22-36	22-36	22-36	22-36
Topography (t)						
Slope (%)	< 3	<3	<2	<2	<3	<2
Wetness (w) Drainage						
	Well drained	Poorly drained	Poorly drained	Well drained	Well drained	Well Drained
Soil physical characteristic (S)						
Texture	SL	SCL	SL	SL	SL	SCL
Soil depth (cm)	150	125	80	133	130	120
Soil fertility (f)						
CEC (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	7.48	8.94	6.68	5.10	5.43	4.87
BS (%)	89.50	87	82	72.20	89.13	77.90
pH	6.46	6.07	6.24	6.69	6.46	6.63
Total nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	0.79	1.04	0.94	0.83	1.39	1.03
Av. Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	7.50	9.14	6.84	8.35	7.32	7.64
Exch. Potassium (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.19	0.17	0.14	0.25	0.09	0.31

Table 2. Land/Soil Characteristics of the Sites in Ebonyi States

Land characteristics	Inyimagu Pedon 7	Igbagu Pedon 8	Abofia Pedon 9	Ugwuukwu Pedon 10	Oziza Pedon 11	Amoso Pedon 12
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	1800- 2300	1800-2300	1800-2300	1800-2300	1800- 2300	1800-2300
Temperature (°C)	23-37	23-37	23-37	23-37	23-37	23-37
Topography (t)						
Slope (%)	< 2	<2	<2	<6	<6	<6
Wetness (w) Drainage						
	Well drained	Poorly drained	Poorly drained	Well drained	Well drained	Well drained
Soil physical characteristic (S)						
Texture	SCL	SCL	SCL	SL	SCL	SCL
Soil depth (cm)	120	50	70	109	120	103
Soil fertility (f)						
CEC (cmol _c kg ⁻¹)	8.99	11.23	9.12	6.75	8.32	6.01
BS (%)	37.75	64.87	61.23	57.43	54.85	61.39
pH	6.04	7.14	6.15	6.06	5.62	6.48
Total nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	0.84	1.46	1.43	0.88	1.13	0.30
Av. Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	11.91	12.43	8.28	9.40	7.39	6.96
Exch. Potassium (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.35	0.54	0.36	0.16	0.34	0.09

Table 3. Land/Soil Characteristics of the Sites in Anambra States

Land characteristics	Oba Pedon 13	Oraifite Pedon 14	Ojoto Pedon 15	Neni Pedon 16	Umuona Pedon 17	Nanka Pedon 18
Climate (c)						
Annual rainfall (mm)	1500-3000	1500-3000	1500-3000	1500-3000	1500-3000	1500-3000
Temperature (°C)	22-37	22-37	22-37	22-37	22-37	22-37
Topography (t)						
Slope(%)	< 4	<4	<5	<2	<2	<1
Wetness (w)						
Drainage	Well drained	Well drained	Well drained	Well drained	Well drained	Well drained
Soil physical characteristic (S)						
Texture	LS	SL	LS	SL	SCL	SL
Soil depth (cm)	156	148	150	149	150	125
Soil fertility (f)						
CEC (cmol ₊ kg ⁻¹)	6.75	8.32	6.01	4.88	4.03	4.53
BS (%)	57.43	54.85	61.39	72.41	60.15	55.64
pH	5.59	5.92	5.59	5.86	5.83	5.47
Total nitrogen (g kg ⁻¹)	0.70	0.74	0.47	0.60	1.27	0.86
Av. Phosphorus (mg kg ⁻¹)	8.08	7.83	7.14	7.21	7.27	7.36
Exch. Potassium (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.05	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.07	0.04

Table 4. Land and Soil Requirements for Cassava (Source: Sys et al., 1991).

Land Quality / Land Characteristics	Units	S1 100 – 95	S2 94 – 85	S3 84 – 40	N1 39 – 20
Climate (c)					
Rainfall	mm	1500 - 1100	1100 – 900	900 – 500	<500
Temperature	°C	18 – 30	> 16	>12	Any
Wetness (w)					
Drainage		Well Drained	Moderately Imperfectly drained	Poorly drained	Very poorly drained
Fertility (f)					
TN (0-15cm depth)	%	>0.2	0.1 – 0.2	<0.1	Any
Available P.	mg kg ⁻¹	> 25	6 – 25	< 6	Any
Exchangeable K	cmolkg ⁻¹	>6	3 – 6	<3	Any
pH		6.1 – 7.3	5.1 – 6.0	>8.4, <4.0	Any
Base Saturation	%	50 – 35	35 – 20	20 – 15	< 15
Soil Physical Characteristics					
Topography	%	0 – 5	5 – 12	12 – 20	>20
Soil Texture		Sandy Clay Loam	Loamy Sand	Clay	Sand
Soil Depth	cm	>100	100 – 75	75 - 50	<50

Table 5. Suitability Assessment of the Sites of Enugu States for Cassava Cultivation

Land Quality / Land Characteristics	Units	Ojor Pedon 1	Asaba Pedon 2	Ogwurugwu Pedon 3	Uhunowere Pedon 4	Ovoko Pedon 5	Enugu-Ezike Pedon 6
Climate (c)							
Rainfall	Mm	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)
Temperature	°C	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)
Wetness (w)							
Drainage		S1(100)	S3(84)	S3(84)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Fertility (f)							
Total Nitrogen (0-15cm)	%	S2 (85)	S2(94)	S2(90)	S3 (84)	S2(90)	S2 (90))
Avail. P	mgkg ⁻¹	S2 (85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2 (85)	S2 (85)	S2 (85)
Exch. K	Cmol/kg	N1 (20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)
pH		S1 (95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1 (95)	S1 (95)	S1 (95)
CEC		S2(90)	S2(90)	S2(90)	S2(85)	S2 (85)	S2 (85)
Base Saturation	%	S1 (100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)
Soil Physical Characteristics(s)							
Soil Texture		S2(90)	S1 (95)	S2(90)	S2(90)	S2(90)	S1(95)
Soil Depth	cm	S1 (100)	S1 (95)	S2(90)	S1(100)	S1 (100)	S1 (95)
Topography (t)	%	S1 (100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1 (100)	S1 (100)
Aggregate suitability rating							
Current Suitability	Parametric	18.97	17.87	17.39	18.97	18.97	19.49
	Non Parametric	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)
	Parametric						
Potential Suitability	Parametric	90.00	81.87	79.69	90.00	90.00	95.00
	Non Parametric	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1
	Parametric						

In Ebonyi State, total nitrogen was moderately suitable in all the soils studied except in Abofia where it was optimum and in Ugwuukwu where it was marginally suitable. Texture was also optimum except in Amoso where it was moderately suitable. Depth was optimum in most sites except in Igbeagu and Abofia where were marginally suitable for cassava production. In Anambra State, total nitrogen was moderately suitable in most soils studied except in Umuona and Nanka where it was optimum. For the aggregate suitability for cassava production, the soils studied were currently not suitable (N1) for cassava production due to fertility constraint. The potential suitability score indicated that most of the soils studied were optimum for cassava production when all the fertility constraints were removed.

Table 6. Suitability Assessment of the Sites of Ebonyi States for Cassava Cultivation

Land Quality / Land Characteristics	Units	Inyimagu Pedon 7	Igbeagu Pedon 8	Abofia Pedon 9	Ugwuukwu Pedon 10	Oziza Pedon 11	Amoso Pedon 12
Climate (c)							
Rainfall	mm	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Temperature	°C	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Wetness (w)							
Drainage		S1(100)	S3(84)	S3(84)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Fertility (f)							
Total Nitrogen (0-15cm)	%	S2(85)	S2(94)	S1(95)	S2 (85)	S2(85)	S3 (70))
Avail. P	mgkg ⁻¹	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)
Exch. K	Cmol/kg	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)
pH		S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)
CEC		S2(90)	S2(90)	S2(90)	S2(85)	S2(90)	S2(85)
Base Saturation	%	S1(95)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Soil Physical Characteristics(s)							
Soil Texture		S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S2(90)	S1(95)	S1(95)
Soil Depth	cm	S1(100)	S3(40)	S3(80)	S1(95)	S1(100)	S1(95)
Topography (t)	%	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)
Aggregate suitability rating							
Current Suitability	Parametric	19.4	11.5	16.40	18.49	19.00	19.00
	Non Parametric	N1(f)	N2(fsw)	N1(fsw)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)
Potential Suitability	Parametric	95.00	36.67	73.32	87.72	92.59	92.59
	Non Parametric	S1	S3(fs)	S2(fw)	S1	S1	S1

Table 7. Suitability Assessment of the Sites of Anambra States for Cassava Cultivation

Land Quality / Land Characteristics	Units	Oba Pedon 7	Oraifite Pedon 8	Ojoto Pedon 9	Neni Pedon 10	Umuona Pedon 11	Nanka Pedon 12
Climate (c)							
Rainfall	mm	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Temperature	°C	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Wetness (w)							
Drainage		S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Fertility (f)							
Total Nitrogen (0-15cm)	%	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2 (85)	S1(95)	S1 (95)
Avail. P	mgkg ⁻¹	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)
Exch. K	Cmol/kg	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)	N1(20)
pH		S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)
CEC		S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)
Base Saturation	%	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Soil Physical Characteristics(s)							
Soil Texture		S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S2(85)	S1(95)	S2(85)
Soil Depth	cm	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Topography (t)	%	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(95)	S1(100)	S1(100)	S1(100)
Aggregate suitability rating							
Current Suitability	Parametric	17.97	17.97	17.97	18.44	19.49	18.44
	Non Parametric	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)	N1(f)
Potential Suitability	Parametric	82.84	82.84	82.84	85.00	95.00	85.84
	Non Parametric	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1	S1

Geostatistics

Descriptive Statistics

The results of the descriptive statistics were shown in Table 8. The interpolation method that are used to generate a surface gives the best result if the data is normally distributed. The log normal transformation was done to the parametric suitability score for cassava (Potential) according to Shapiro–Wilk test. The results were skewed to the left with cassava (potential) having the higher outlier. The results also indicated low coefficient of variation (CV).

Semivariogram

The results of the semivariogram were presented in Table 9, and Semivariogram parameters (range, nugget, and sill) for each soil property with the best-fitted model were shown in Figure 1 (current) and Figure 2 (potential). Karl et al., (2010) noted that an ideal situation would consist of a small nugget and a large sill. This would also implies that much spatial dependence exist among the data and a lot could be inferred about an unobserved location depending on its distance from an observed site. The result from the parametric suitability for crops showed that Exponential model was best fitted for cassava (C i.e. Current) having none log normal transformation while Spherical Model was best fitted for cassava (P i.e. Potential) having log normal transformation. Both falls within strong spatial class with cassava (Potential) having the lowest nugget effect.

Table 8. Descriptive Statistics from Parametric Suitability of Cassava

Crop	Trans. type	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	CV	Skewness	Kurtosis
Cassava (C)	None	18.096	18.465	11.500	19.490	1.829	10.109	-2.779	10.653
Cassava (P)	Log	4.418	4.463	3.602	4.554	0.215	4.871	-3.232	12.897

Table 9. Semivariogram Parameter for Cassava Suitability

Crop	Data Trans	Model	Nugget	Partial Sill	Sill	Range	Spatial Ratio	Spatial Class
Cassava (C)	None	Exponential	0.333	2.846	3.179	14143.27	10.47	strong
Cassava (P)	Log	Spherical	0.011	0.0358	0.0471	14143.27	23.99	strong

Fig. 1. Semivariogram for Cassava (Current).

Fig. 2. Semivariogram for Cassava (Potential).

Regression function $-0.0269 * x + 18.77$

Prediction Errors

Samples 18 of 18
 Mean 0.0161
 Root-Mean-Square 2.12385
 Mean Standardized 0.0019
 Root-Mean-Square Standardized 1.1838
 Average Standard Error 1.7111

Fig. 3. Cross Validation for Cassava (Current)

Regression function $-0.0686 * x + 92.07$

Prediction Errors

Samples 18 of 18
 Mean 0.3521
 Root-Mean-Square 16.89
 Mean Standardized -0.0548
 Root-Mean-Square Standardized 1.0119
 Average Standard Error 17.7098

Fig. 4. Cross Validation for Cassava (Potential)

Cross Validation

The results from cross validation were presented in Figure 3 (current) and Figure 4 (Potential). These results were obtained by omitting a point (measured value), and the rest of the results were used to predict the value (predicted value) of this omitted point (measured point). The predicted value was then used to compare the measured value. According to ESRI (2020), for a prediction to be valid, the blue line and the gray line (1:1 line) should be close to each other, the Mean Error (ME) should be close to zero, the Root-Mean-Square Prediction Errors (RMSPE) and the Average Standard Error (ASE) should be close one another and the Root Mean Squared Standardized Error (RMSSE) should be close to one. The results of the cross validation showed that

the models made moderate prediction in the variability of the suitability of cassava because the Mean Error (ME) is close to zero, the Root-Mean-Square Prediction Errors (RMSPE) and the Average Standard Error (ASE) were close one another and the Root Mean Squared Standardized Error (RMSSE) was close to one even though the blue line and the gray line (1:1 line) are farther apart. This could be as a result of limited sampled point.

Fig. 5. Current Suitability Map for Cassava

Fig. 6. Potential Suitability Map for Cassava.

Kriged Map

From the Kriged map for suitability of cassava (Current) shown in Figure 5, all the study areas were generally (temporally) not suitable for cassava production with areas in Ebonyi State showing the lowest suitability score (as low as 11.5 to 15.47). When the fertility constraints were

removed (potentially) as shown in Figure 7, the study area became highly suitable for cassava production with suitability score between 83.99 to 92.74 covering large area of the study area with very few places indicating moderately suitable.

Conclusion

Cassava, one of the most popular cash crop in Southeastern Nigeria is mostly grown on acidic, low fertility, low organic matter with high level of aluminium soils. The result from the parametric scores indicate that all the studied soils are potentially highly to moderately suitable for cassava production. This study revealed that cassava production will be immensely increased if fertility constraints opposing this soils are met. The looming famine that increase in population will impose on the people of Southeastern Nigeria will be reduced significantly if cautious efforts are made by cassava growers to improve the fertility of the soils of this area.

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